

Simulation of Solar Water Collector Stagnation Temperature

Central Solar Water Heating

Multi-Apartment Residential Buildings in Tel Aviv

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Abstract

This publication introduces the simulation procedure of solar water collector stagnation temperature. The calculations are for central solar water heating systems in multi-apartment residential buildings in Tel Aviv. The stagnation may be caused by the system's circulation pump being shut down by incorrect pump control. The stagnation temperature depends on the collector efficiency, which depends on the collector temperature. This results in circular calculations, which may be solved by computer simulation. The integration interval of the simulation is 1 minute. For the selected solar collector and the typical weather in Tel Aviv, the maximum stagnation temperature is 150°C in August. On extremely hot days the calculated stagnation temperature may reach 209°C. Solar water collector reaches 50°C stagnation temperature in 2.7 hours after sunrise, and 60°C in 3.1 hours, on average.

Glossary

a, b	coefficients of the solar collector efficiency formula $\eta = a \cdot x + b$
c	specific heat of the collector components, kcal/kg°C
kcal	kilo-calorie, energy unit
MC	thermal mass of the solar collector, kcal/°C
Q	heat flow (energy in time), kcal/minute (not kcal)
SE	global solar energy, W/m ² or kcal/minute,m ²
SE _{kcal}	global solar energy expressed in kcal/minute,m ²
SE _W	global solar energy expressed in W/,m ²
SWH	Solar Water Heater, in this work central, forced circulation solar water heating system in multi-apartment residential buildings
T _a	ambient temperature, °C
T _m	solar collector mean temperature, °C
x	independent variable in the collector efficiency equation, axis x on graphic presentation of the efficiency, °C*m ² /W
α	absorptance of solar collector
ε	emissivity of solar collector
η	collector's efficiency

Introduction

Solar water heaters must be installed in new buildings in Israel according to the law. Solar water heaters save 5 % of the national electricity consumption [1] and are an important component of the Israeli economy and standard of living. The solar law requires solar water heaters for 9 upper floors of the residential buildings.

The usual solution for residential buildings above 4 floors is a forced circulation system with a central collectors array and individual storage tanks separate for each apartment.

In this work, the stagnation is caused by shutting down the system circulation pump.

This may happen due to incorrect control of the circulation pump.

This work is for conditions in Israel/Tel Aviv.

Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually, metric units apply Joule as an energy unit. In this work, the energy unit is kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal. Application of kcal instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference immediately indicates the amount of energy in kcal.

Local time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST is not considered in this work.

Solar Water Heater

The solar water heating system selected for this work is Chromagen and consists of the following main parts:

- central collectors array
- individual 150 liter vertical storage tanks with inside 2.5kW instant backup
- circulation pump

Location: Tel Aviv / Israel 32.0929° N, 34.8072° E

Tilt Angle

The tilt angle for central solar installations in residential buildings in Israel is 45° [1].

Selected Solar Collector

The selected solar collector for this work is Chromagen F (CR120) 16mm selective paint [4].

Table 1 - Selected solar collector [4]

Standard capacity [1] [kcal/day]	7,110
Risers diameter [mm]	16
Gross area [m ²]	2.77
Aperture area [m ²]	2.56
Length [cm]	2.18
Width [cm]	1.27
Weight [kg]	43
Fluid capacity [L]	4.13
Thermal mass, MC [kcal/°C]	9.88
Absorptance, α	0.90
Emissivity, ε	0.45
Linear efficiency coefficient a	-4.80
Linear efficiency coefficient b	0.72
Stagnation temperature [°C]	170

As the solar energy data are for 1 m², also the collector data will be for 1 m² of its net opening.

Table 2 - Thermal Mass, MC [4]

		Collector	/m2
Opening	m2	2.56	1.00
Weight	kg	43	16.80
Weight Cu	kg		8.40
Weight Al	kg		5.04
Weight Steel	kg		3.36
Weight Water	kg	4.1	1.60
c CU	kcal/kg, °C		0.09
c Al	kcal/kg, °C		0.21
c Steel	kcal/kg, °C		0.12
mc Cu	kcal/°C,m2		0.77
mc Al	kcal/°C,m2		1.08
mc Steel	kcal/°C,m2		0.40
mc Water	kcal/°C,m2		1.60
Thermal Mass, MC	kcal/°C	9.88	3.86

Solar Radiation

Solar radiation data on the horizontal surface for a typical year in Tel Aviv is from [2].

Solar radiation data on the horizontal surface for the hottest day in Tel Aviv in 2024 is from [6].

Solar radiation data in a typical year on a tilt angle of 45° in Tel Aviv is from [7].

Chart 1 - Solar radiation in typical year in Tel Aviv on tilt angle 45°, W/m² [2] [3]

Ambient Air Temperature

Chart 2 - Ambient air temperature in typical year in Tel Aviv, °C [2]

Ambient air temperature data for a typical year in Tel Aviv is from [2].

Solar Collector Initial Temperature

In this work, the initial temperature of the solar collector is the ambient air temperature at sunrise, which means that the solar collector was not in the stagnation condition a day before the determination of the stagnation temperature.

Table 3 - Sunrise and sunset time, and initial temperature of the solar collector (on 15 each month)

	Sunrise on 15	Initial Temperature, °C	Sunset on 15
January	6:41	7.7	16:58
February	6:23	8.8	17:26
March	5:51	9.2	17:48
April	5:12	13.3	18:10
May	4:43	15.0	18:31
June	4:34	18.2	18:49
July	4:45	19.8	18:48
August	5:05	20.2	18:25
September	5:24	18.8	17:47
October	5:44	16.1	17:08
November	6:09	11.2	16:41
December	6:33	8.1	16:37

Heat Transfer

Definition of specific heat:

$$c = (1 / m) * (dQ / dt)$$

$$dQ = m * c * dt$$

dQ heat flow, in our case solar energy absorbed by the solar collector, kcal/minute

m mass of the solar collector, including water inside the collector, kg

c specific heat of each element of the mass of the solar collector, kcal/kg,°C

dt temperature rise from t_0 to t_1 caused by the solar radiation (the heat flow) in a period of time, in this work °C/minute

$$MC = m * c$$
$$dt = (t_1 - t_0) / \Delta Time$$

MC thermal mass of the solar collector, calculated in section "*Selected Solar Collector*" above, kcal/°C

$\Delta Time$ Integration Interval of the simulation, in this work $\Delta Time$ is 1 minute

$$dQ = MC * (t_1 - t_0) / \Delta Time$$
$$t_1 = t_0 + dQ * \Delta Time / MC$$

t_0 of the current simulation step equals t_1 of the previous simulation step

$$dQ = SE_{kcal} * \eta$$

dQ heat flow, in our case solar energy absorbed by the solar collector, kcal/minute

SE_{kcal} global solar energy on the collector tilt angle expressed in kcal/minute, in difference to SE_W used for determination of the solar collector efficiency, which is expressed in Watts

η solar collector efficiency as defined in the next section

Solar Collector Efficiency

Solar collector efficiency is calculated as explained in publication [5].

All solar collector efficiency calculations are related to 1 m² of the solar collector net opening to the sun.

$$\eta = a \cdot x + b$$

$$x = (T_m - T_a) / SEW$$

η solar collector efficiency at point x
 x independent variable, axis x on graphic presentation of the efficiency, °C*m²/W

a, b coefficients of the efficiency formula, must be published by the solar collector manufacturer in Israel for the selected collector [4]:

$$a = -4.80$$

$$b = +0.72$$

T_m mean temperature of the collector, °C
 $T_m = t_1$

T_a ambient air temperature, °C

SEW global solar energy on the collector tilt angle expressed in W/m², in difference to SE_{kcal} used for determination of the collector temperature, which is kcal/minute

Formula 1 - Solar collector efficiency

$$\eta = a * (T_m - T_a) / SEW + b$$

To avoid circular calculation, the efficiency of the solar collector is calculated based on the collector temperature as determined in the previous step (previous minute) of the simulation.

Stagnation Temperature

Table 4 - Stagnation temperature, °C

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
7:00					38	39	37	33	34			
8:00	19	23	29	45	59	59	53	51	58	51	46	19
9:00	41	51	53	70	84	82	72	77	88	87	75	43
10:00	65	75	79	95	106	106	97	104	108	116	100	72
11:00	87	90	102	117	124	126	121	127	121	123	118	96
12:00	103	99	120	130	134	139	136	144	141	122	126	106
13:00	112	106	131	136	136	144	143	150	145	126	125	107
14:00	107	110	130	128	129	140	141	146	142	119	114	94
15:00	90	95	118	110	114	126	130	135	126	98	93	91
16:00	68	80	97	90	92	107	112	114	97	76	65	75
17:00		63	70	67	68	84	88	87	72	56	41	44
18:00			44	45	48	61	64	61	50	38		

Maximum Monthly Stagnation Temperature

The following table indicates the time when the maximum stagnation temperature occurred.

Table 5 - Maximum monthly stagnation temperature, °C

		°C	Efficiency
January	13:14	112	0.062%
February	14:03	110	0.058%
March	14:23	132	0.018%
April	13:08	137	0.168%
May	12:48	136	0.055%
June	13:03	144	0.096%
July	13:15	143	0.043%
August	12:48	150	0.101%
September	12:37	147	0.082%
October	13:12	127	0.265%
November	12:21	127	0.069%
December	13:00	107	0.014%

Time When Stagnation Reaches 50°C and 60°C

Table 6 - The time when stagnation reaches 50°C

	Sunrise	50°C	time from sunrise, hr
January	6:41	9:23	2.7
February	6:23	8:59	2.6
March	5:51	8:54	3.1
April	5:12	8:14	3.0
May	4:43	7:38	2.9
June	4:34	7:36	3.0
July	4:45	7:49	3.1
August	5:05	7:59	2.9
September	5:24	7:43	2.3
October	5:44	7:58	2.2
November	6:09	8:09	2.0
December	6:33	9:14	2.7
Ave			2.7

Table 7 - The time when stagnation reaches 60°C

	Sunrise		time from sunrise, hr
January	6:41	9:48	3.1
February	6:23	9:19	2.9
March	5:51	9:16	3.4
April	5:12	8:38	3.4
May	4:43	8:04	3.4
June	4:34	8:03	3.5
July	4:45	8:23	3.6
August	5:05	8:24	3.3
September	5:24	8:04	2.7
October	5:44	8:19	2.6
November	6:09	8:29	2.3
December	6:33	9:35	3.0
Ave			3.1

The Hottest Day

The hottest day in Tel Aviv in 2024 till the time of this work (12 July 2024) was on 25 April 2024, 41.5°C at 13:40. The highest solar radiation on this day was 1,123 W/m² at 10:50 [6].

Chart 3 - Ambient temperature in Tel Aviv on 25 April 2024, °C [6]

Chart 4 - Global solar radiation in Tel Aviv on 25 April 2024, W/m² [6]

Chart 5 - Solar collector efficiency on 25 April 2024

Chart 6 - Solar collector stagnation temperature on 25 April 2024, °C

Table 8 - Stagnation temperature on 25 April 2024, °C

	°C
6:00	32
7:00	61
8:00	99
9:00	138
10:00	170
11:00	196
12:00	205
13:00	208
14:00	199

Maximum stagnation temperature on 25 April 2024 was 209°C at 12:14.

1. Reference

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